

MAAL: a multi-agent autonomous live looper for improvised co-creation of musical structures

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Abstract

Live looping is a musical practice based on recording, repetition and layering segments of a live music performance. Layering loops is a technique used to create musical structures that evolve over time throughout a performance, and it is particularly popular among solo improvising musicians. This paper presents the Multi-Agent Autonomous Looper – a system that autonomously selects musical segments to be sampled and looped during a live performance, using a set of rule-based agents. Each loop track is managed by an agent that listens to the musician’s performance and to the concurrently looping segments on other tracks. The decision on which segments of the performance to loop depends on user-selected rules based on comparison of musical properties, expressing varying degrees of sonic compatibility. This approach characterizes the entire system as a multi-agent network capable of autonomously generating emergent musical structures throughout a performance. The Multi-Agent Autonomous Looper aims to expand the possibilities for indirect control and co-creative interactions in live looping for improvising musicians. In the paper, we detail the system’s objectives and design, its offline and online implementations, and discuss specific settings and behaviors across three representative use cases.

1 Introduction

Live looping is a popular practice among improvising musicians across musical styles. During a live looping performance, musicians record musical segments which are then played back repeatedly. When using a looping device, musicians trigger the start and stop of the sound recording. Once the recording stops, the recorded audio segment typically starts looping immediately. During a performance, musicians can layer several loops, experimenting with the harmonic and rhythmic relations between them to develop musical structures that evolve over time (Duarte and Sardo, 2023). Depending on the features of the looper, performers may additionally control the duration, playback speed, and audio processing applied to each loop track.

Controlling a looper while improvising with an instrument in a live setting is a complex process that requires careful planning and execution of musical ideas. When recording a new loop, musicians make decisions on how its rhythmic, harmonic, timbral, and melodic aspects will interlock within the previously recorded ongoing loops. In this work, we explore the creative possibilities that emerge from automating the selection and management of audio segments to be looped during a live performance using a network of rule-based autonomous agents. In particular, we explore the creative opportunities that arise from a machine’s ability to listen to and evaluate sound differently

from a live musician, offering a unique qualitative perspective. Computers can process information in parallel, allowing for distinct evaluation of music material for each loop track, thereby automating the coherent and simultaneous musical control of a potentially very large number of loop tracks. This expansion allows for co-performance and indirect interaction with a looper exhibiting degrees of autonomy, while human intervention remains essential for defining the rules used by various agents and creating musical material during the performance. The layered looped segments determine the musical structure of the performance, in turn stimulating the musician to adapt their improvisation to the looper's decisions, generating a continuous co-creative interaction (Davis et al., 2015).

The Multi-Agent Autonomous Looper (MAAL) automates loop selection by associating a rule-based agent with each track. These agents autonomously evaluate the compatibility of candidate loop segments by analyzing specific sound features and comparing them with segments on other tracks. The rules are inspired by the criteria musicians might use when deciding to loop a segment of their performance, such as evaluating rhythmic compatibility, harmonic and contrapuntal relationships. The interaction between loop tracks can be modeled as a multi-agent system, where agents have an interdependent relationship, listening to each other (Sanfilippo et al., 2012). A change in the contents of a loop track influences the future decisions of agents controlling the other loop tracks, enabling the system to exhibit global emergent behavior.

2 Background

2.1 Autonomy and co-creation in interactive music systems

Computer programs are considered autonomous agents when they are situated within an environment, they can sense it and act on it over time, affecting what they will sense in the future and in pursuit of their own goals (Franklin and Graesser, 1996). The application of software agents in creative tasks is explored as human-machine co-creation, where human and machine decision-making merge to create a shared artifact (Wen et al., 2015; Davis et al., 2015). In this context, computational co-creative systems are defined as collaborative creative activities involving at least one computational agent (Karimi et al., 2018). Davis et al. (2015) highlight synchronous collaboration during the creative process as a fundamental trait of co-creative systems, which Yannakakis et al. (2014) describe as *mixed initiative* when this involves a turn-taking process.

The design of autonomous co-creative agents has been a significant focus in live electronic composition. Advances in digital signal processing and artificial intelligence have expanded the creative possibilities of interactive music systems for live performance, enabling the detection of perceptually relevant sound features and the automated control of sound models with increasing nuance and complexity (Rowe, 1992a). Blackwell et al. (2012) formalize the design of co-creative agents for music improvisation as *live algorithms*. They describe a *live algorithm* as an interactive music system capable of analyzing audio input from a live musician, and responding by controlling an arbitrary sound model.

Rule-based systems have historically been the earliest form of Artificial Intelligence (AI) used in music. The *Illiad Suite*, considered the first computer-generated music composition, was programmed as a rule-based system (Sandred et al., 2009). Rule-based systems are also frequently used in performance-driven interactive music systems, as in George Lewis's *Voyager* (Steinbeck, 2018), which generates symbolic music based on machine listening of live audio features. Rule-based systems typically apply rules grounded on music theory, which are explicitly encoded to reflect the aesthetic preferences and compositional domain of the designer and/or the user (Magnusson, 2019). According to Tatar and Pasquier (2019), such systems can be categorized as rule-based reactive agents, extracting musical information such as melody, pitch class, key, harmony, rhythm, timbre, loudness and note density (Gifford et al., 2018). These agents can respond by transforming input data and triggering events, such as playing back samples from a corpus, generating control data or symbolic notation, or synthesizing audio. Rule-based agents have been employed for tasks such as free improvisation (Collins, 2011; Hsu, 2010), melody generation (Thom, 2000; Rowe, 1992b), and rhythm generation (Murray-Rust et al., 2005). When integrated into feedback networks, agents can produce emergent behavior such as coordination and structure formation (Serugendo et al., 2005). These properties have been explored in swarm music systems (Fasciani et al., 2024) and feedback systems (Sanfilippo, 2021).

2.2 Live sampling and looping

A loop is a musical element with a precise time duration, typically lasting a few seconds. In Curtis Roads’ framework of time structures in musical perception, loops can be considered *meso*-level elements (Roads, 2003). Roads describes the *meso*-level as a *local* time scale, with durations approximately from 100 milliseconds up to 8 seconds. Common musical mesostructures at this level are melodic and rhythmic phrases. Events at this time scale, described by Wishart (1994) as *sequences*, are where *sound objects* are organized into patterns. Simultaneously playing mesostructures are perceived in terms of harmonic, contrapuntal and rhythmic relationships.

The ability of digital instruments to record sounds during a performance opens numerous possibilities for engaging with repetition across various time scales. These include tools and instrumental practices that utilize live sampled sequences, ranging from live granular manipulation—exemplified by Barry Truax’s real-time granular compositions (Truax, 1994)—to the long delay lines featured in Pauline Overos’s *Expanded Instrument System* (Oliveros, 1991). Sampling and manipulation of sound from live musicians is a common feature in interactive music systems for live electronic improvisation (Van Nort et al., 2013; Lippit, 2004), and numerous control methods have been developed to facilitate the live organization and playback of pre-recorded samples during performance (Argo, 2004; Kobayashi et al., 2020; Advincula et al., 2019; Han and Kakehi, 2020). Co-creative instruments like GREIS (Van Nort et al., 2010), FILTER (Van Nort et al., 2012), and CAVI (Erdem et al., 2022) use mapping strategies to control live sampling, delays and audio processing, thereby ‘expanding’ live instruments. Other system, such as MASOM (Tatar and Pasquier, 2017), Somax (Assayag et al., 2022), Spire Muse (Thelle and Pasquier, 2021), MACAT and MACataRT (Lee and Pasquier, 2025), focus on the responsive concatenative recombination of sounds or symbolic music from a predefined corpus.

In recent years, several co-improvisation systems based on autonomous control of looping devices have been proposed (Frisson et al., 2021; Barbosa et al., 2017). The Reflexive Looper (Pachet et al., 2013; Marchini et al., 2017) utilizes a chord sequence to contextually control the concatenation of bars previously played by musicians, thereby accompanying a live improvisation. This system distinguishes the musician’s playing mode as melody, bass or harmony, and matches the accompaniment to the predefined chord grid. Wallace and Martin (2019) developed a harmony prediction algorithm to control accompaniment with concatenative synthesis of samples selected by the musician during performance to complement user-selected loops, dynamically adapting the harmony as new layers are selected. Other systems modify the sound material within the loops selected by users. The Living Looper (Shepardson and Magnusson, 2023; Shepardson et al., 2025), for example, uses RAVE autoencoders (Caillon and Esling, 2021) to autonomously generate contextual variations over user-defined loops. Similarly, the Concentric Sampler records and processes sounds from a floppy disk (Tate, 2022).

The reviewed looping systems utilize predefined temporal structures, musical roles, and concepts like chord sequences or user-selected loops. Conversely, the proposed autonomous looper functions without predefined time structures, relying only on user-customizable sound and music-based rules for decision-making. This flexibility makes it ideal for improvisational contexts and musical genres where discrete structures and chord-based harmony might not apply. Unlike earlier intelligent loopers that adapt their accompaniment to a musician’s improvisation, our looper assesses compatibility based solely on musician-generated audio segments within the concurrent looping material selected by the system’s agents. Musicians using our looper must adapt to the musical structures created by looping segments of their performance, as they cannot choose which parts are selected for looping.

3 Multi-Agent Autonomous Looper

The Multi-Agent Autonomous Looper introduced in this paper determines optimal looping points within a musician’s live performance by analyzing its musical content in real time. There are two possible approaches to designing such a system.

The first approach is prediction-based, where the decision to record and loop a segment occurs ahead of the musician performing it. This requires developing a predictive model that anticipates what the musician will play and assesses its suitability for looping. While this approach mirrors a typical interaction between a performer and a looper, allowing immediate looping of segments, it poses challenges in generating accurate predictions, especially in improvisational scenarios. Personalization

is necessary due to individual performance differences, and prediction errors can disrupt musical layering. The second approach is listening-based, where the musician’s sound is continuously recorded and analyzed to decide what to add or replace in the looping tracks. This method offers accurate sound analysis, enabling evaluation of how new segments will blend with existing loops. However, it introduces latency, as aligning loops requires the newly accepted segment to wait until the next looping cycle begins. In this paper, we employ a listening-based approach, prioritizing accuracy over latency.

3.1 Computational model of a looper and autonomous decision-making

The MAAL works by analyzing segments of the live performance of an improvising musician according to *meso*-level descriptors, assessing whether the segments’ musical properties can integrate within other concurrent loops, guided by predefined rules based on user-specified musical objectives. In this section, we describe the computational model of our live looper and the mechanism it uses for autonomous decision-making.

A looper is a system capable of storing and continuously reproducing (i.e., looping) recorded sound across an arbitrary number of independent tracks. Our computational model supports an arbitrary number N of loop tracks L_n , with loop track index $n \in \mathbb{N} : n \in [1, N]$. The model assumes a common tempo between the musician and the looper, as if synchronized by a metronome. While this may be impractical in some contexts, most situations can theoretically adapt by using tempo and beat-tracking algorithms to create a metronome signal for the looper. This integration is beyond the scope of this paper.

The MAAL analyzes non-overlapping, consecutive segments of the musician’s live audio signal $x(t)$, with segments having a fixed duration T_u , synchronized with the metronome grid. T_u is expressed in musical duration, as a number of beats, with its actual temporal duration determined by the tempo. The system updates every T_u , potentially modifying the audio buffer for loop tracks that store segments of duration T_l , also expressed as several beats. For simplicity, we assume $T_u = T_l$, though the system design can accommodate different values. We use a discrete-time index m , incrementing every interval T_u , to define segments $s[m]$ of $x(t)$, as shown in equation 1. While T_u can be any value, the system targets *meso*-level audio structures, with typical durations from 100 ms to 8 s, capturing sequences of sonic events.

$$s[m] = x(t), \quad \text{with } t \in [t + (m - 1)T_u, t + mT_u) \quad (1)$$

At any time m , a loop track L_n ’s audio buffer $l_n[m]$ can either be empty, denoted as $l_n[m] = 0$, or contain a previously selected segment, represented as $l_n[m] = s[m_n]$, where m_n is the time index at which prior segment of the musician’s audio signal was stored in track L_n ’s buffer. The looper’s output at time m , as shown in equation 2, is the sum of all loop tracks, with unique m_n values, as each segment $s[m]$ can be stored in at most one loop track. Using a machine-listening approach, segments $s[m]$ require analysis before possibly being stored in any of the N loop tracks’ buffers. Since this analysis takes computational time, and system updates occur at discrete m steps, a full T_u interval must pass before updating the contents of any loop track. Once a segment is deemed suitable for looping, the system waits for the completion of the T_u interval before updating the loop tracks’ buffers, resulting in a latency of one update cycle, T_u . For this reason, T_u sets the time constraint for analysis, ensuring real-time performance. Typically extending over several seconds, T_u provides adequate computational time for complex analysis over a possibly large number of loop tracks.

$$\text{out}[m] = \sum_{n=1}^N l_n[m] = \sum_{n=1}^N s[m_n], \quad \text{with } m_1 \neq m_2 \neq \dots \neq m_N \quad (2)$$

When recording a looping segment, a musician takes aesthetic decisions regarding how the harmonic, melodic, rhythmic, dynamic, and/or timbral characteristics of the new segment will interlock within the segments concurrently looping. In improvised performances, these decisions stem from embodied knowledge developed through long-term practice with the instrument, combined with personal aesthetic preferences. In the MAAL, these decision-making behaviors are mimicked by a set of agents, each responsible for controlling the contents of the audio buffer of an individual loop track $l_n[m]$. Each agent takes decisions based on a set ρ_n composed of individual rules $r()$, informed by

machine listening and musical practices, assessing the musical compatibility of the latest segment $s[m]$ against the cumulative contents of the other loop tracks, here represented as $\overline{l_n[m]}$, as in equation 3.

$$\overline{l_n[m]} = \sum_{k=1, k \neq n}^N l_k[m]. \quad (3)$$

A rule $r()$, used for track n , compares the candidate segment $s[m]$ to the sum of the looping segments in the other tracks, $\overline{l_n[m]}$. A rule $r()$ produces a positive real number, denoted as $r() : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$. It utilizes a comparison metric $c() : X \rightarrow [0, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$, a comparison threshold τ where $\tau \in [0, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$, and a comparison coefficient $\xi \in \{-1, 1\}$ to determine whether the satisfaction condition is above or below the threshold. $r()$ returns zero when the rule is violated. Otherwise, it indicates the extent to which the rule is satisfied, reflected by how much the comparison metric exceeds the threshold, as outlined in equation 4.

$$r(s[m], \overline{l_n[m]}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \xi \cdot (c(s[m], \overline{l_n[m]}) - \tau) < 0 \\ \xi \cdot (c(s[m], \overline{l_n[m]}) - \tau), & \text{if } \xi \cdot (c(s[m], \overline{l_n[m]}) - \tau) \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Each loop track L_n can be associated with a set of rules ρ_n rather than a single one. This set comprises an arbitrary number J_n of rules $r_{j,n}$, where each rule is specified by its individual comparison metric function $c_{j,n}()$, threshold $\tau_{j,n}$, and comparison coefficient $\xi_{j,n}$, as summarized in equation 5.

$$\rho_n() = \{r_{j,n}() \mid r_{j,n}() = \{c_{j,n}(), \tau_{j,n}, \xi_{j,n}\}, j \in [1, J_n]\} \quad (5)$$

The set of rules is evaluated using an "and-logic" approach, meaning that all individual rules must be satisfied for the entire rule set to be considered satisfied. If the set is violated, it produces a result of 0. Otherwise, it yields the mean of the values produced by the $r_{j,n}$, as shown in equation 6. This arrangement enables agents to engage in complex reasoning about loop musical compatibility assessment, resulting in a flexible system capable of achieving varied musical objectives by combining several rules. This flexibility is achieved by leveraging a pool of available comparison metrics, $c()$, which are described in Section 3.2.

$$\rho_n(s[m]) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \exists j \in [1, J_n] : r_{j,n}(s[m], \overline{l_n[m]}) = 0 \\ \frac{1}{J_n} \sum_{j=1}^{J_n} r_{j,n}(s[m], \overline{l_n[m]}), & \text{if } \forall j \in [1, J_n] : r_{j,n}(s[m], \overline{l_n[m]}) > 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

If multiple rules are satisfied, $s[m]$ is allocated to the track L_n that satisfies the rule to the greatest extent, ensuring that the same segment is not allocated to multiple loop tracks. The behavior is summarized in the general update rule utilized in the looper, as shown in equation 7. This rule reflects the latency of the machine-listening approach, where during the update cycle linked to time m , the MAAL evaluates the compatibility of $s[m-1]$ for use in the audio buffer of any loop track $l_n[m+1]$. Figure 1 illustrates an example of this update process. The system also allows specifying optional minimum r_{min} and maximum r_{max} numbers of repetitions, or update cycles, during which a segment $s[m]$ is held in each track L_n . This adds an extra layer of control that complements the set of rules, preventing the MAAL output from changing too frequently or maintaining segments for too long. Equation 7 uses m_n to track the duration a loop segment is held. In the first scenario of equation 7, the value m_n is updated to $m-1$.

$$\forall n : l_n[m+1] = \begin{cases} s[m-1], & \text{if } n = \arg \max_{k \in [1, N]} \rho_k(s[m-1]) \mid \rho_k(s[m-1]) > 0 \\ & \text{and } m - m_n > r_{min} \\ 0, & \text{if } m - m_n > r_{max} \\ l_n[m], & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

When all audio buffers for the N loop tracks are empty ($l_n[m] = 0$), such as at the start or when r_{max} is reached for all tracks, update rule 7 fails to allocate any $s[m]$ because the set of rules $\rho_n(s[m])$ in

Figure 1: Illustration representing the MAAL update process over time, with number of tracks $N = 3$. At time m , the segment $s[m-1]$ is allocated to the L_1 audio buffer, looping from time $m+1$, as it produced the highest value among the N loop tracks when compared against $\overline{l_n[m-1]}$ using $\rho_1()$.

equation 6 cannot be satisfied with $\overline{l_n[m]} = 0$. In this state, we use the initialization described in equation 8, comparing segment $s[m]$ to an arbitrary number P of prior segments. The comparison uses the average of the J_n comparison metric $c_{j,n}$ associated with each track L_n . A segment is copied to the audio buffer of loop track N if it exceeds a global threshold ϵ . This selection aims to recognize patterns repeated over $P+1$ consecutive segments by the musician, assuming that such repeated material is significant and should be looped.

$$\forall n : l_n[m+1] = \begin{cases} s[m-1] & \text{if } \frac{1}{P} \frac{1}{J_n} \sum_{p=2}^{P+1} \sum_{j=1}^{J_n} c_{j,n}(s[m-1], s[m-p]) \geq \epsilon \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The MAAL can operate with $T_u \neq T_l$, where T_u is a fraction of the loop duration T_l , defined by d as $T_u = T_l/d$, with $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and $d > 1$. Loop track buffers can hold entire segments or repeated fractions depending on how T_u divides T_l , allowing varied loop durations per track. Equation 9 models this, where \bigcup_d concatenates d segments $x(t)_b$ of duration bT_u . Here, d equals the count of T_u fitting into T_l . Thus, all $s_b[m]$, must be evaluated with update rule 7 at each T_u .

$$s_b[m] = \bigcup_d x(t)_b, \quad \text{where } t \in [t + (m-1)T_l, t + (m-1)T_l + bT_u] \quad (9)$$

3.2 Comparison metrics

The comparison metrics $c()$ assess the similarity between two segments of equal duration, based on specific musical aspects. These metrics yield values between 0 and 1, with 1 indicating high similarity and 0 indicating low or no similarity. As shown in equation 4, these metrics are utilized by agents to assess musical compatibility, determining the presence of a meaningful harmonic, contrapuntal, or rhythmic relationship between the latest segment performed by the musician $s[m-1]$ and the cumulative contents of other loop tracks $\overline{l_n[m-1]}$.

Since the MAAL is designed to be versatile across different types or styles of performances and musical instruments, we provide a pool of comparison metrics $c()$. These metrics serve as building blocks for constructing more complex rule sets $\rho()$, utilized by agents associated with the N loop tracks. Table 1 details the available $c()$, with each metric named to reflect the sonic or musical aspect it compares. Generally, each $c()$ utilizes one or more sequences of descriptors derived from the audio

signals $s[m]$ and $\overline{l_n[m]}$, along with a method for comparing them. The descriptors used within our proposed comparison metrics include onset detection (Hainsworth et al., 2003), chroma pitch class (Stein et al., 2009), fundamental frequency (F0) (Mauch and Dixon, 2014), spectral flatness (Caetano et al., 2019), Mel-scaled spectrum with 40 bands (Logan et al., 2000), tonnetz (Harte et al., 2006) and Root-Mean-Square (RMS) amplitude. These descriptors are calculated on frames of approximately 23 ms with 50% overlap, yielding either a scalar or a vector for each analysis frame, depending on the descriptor. An exception is onset detection, which produces timestamps of the detected onsets.

Table 1: Pool of metrics $c()$, detailing the descriptors and comparison methods utilized. The suffixes C and D indicate continuous and discrete variants. MSE: Mean Squared Error; PCC: Pearson Correlation Coefficient; RMS: Root Mean Square amplitude.

ID	Name of metric $c()$	Descriptors	Comparison method
#1	Harmonic similarity	Chroma	MSE on sequence
#2	Harmonic movement - C	Chroma	PCC on sequence
#3	Harmonic movement - D	Chroma, Onset	PCC at onsets
#4	Melodic similarity	F0	MSE on sequence
#5	Melodic trajectory - C	F0	PCC on sequence
#6	Melodic trajectory - D	F0, Onset	PCC at onsets
#7	Dynamic similarity	RMS	MSE on sequence
#8	Dynamic changes - C	RMS	PCC on sequence
#9	Dynamic changes - D	RMS, Onset	PCC at onsets
#10	Timbral similarity	Flatness	MSE on sequence
#11	Timbral evolution - C	Flatness	PCC on sequence
#12	Timbral evolution - D	Flatness, Onset	PCC at onsets
#13	Global spectral overlap	Mel Spectrum	Difference of averages
#14	Frequency range overlap	Mel Spectrum	Overlap of bandwidths
#15	Rhythmic similarity	Binary Rhythm, Onset	Hamming distance
#16	Rhythmic density	Binary Rhythm, Onset	Difference of onsets number
#17	Harmonic function similarity	Tonnetz	MSE on sequence
#18	Harmonic function transitions - C	Tonnetz	PCC on sequence
#19	Harmonic function transitions - D	Tonnetz, Onset	PCC at onsets

We primarily use two methods to compare the similarity of most descriptor sequences: Mean-Square Error (MSE) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC). For the latter, we employ two variants: one calculates the PCC across the entire sequence of descriptors, and the other considers values only at detected onsets in both segments, thereby focusing on sound events for targeted assessment. MSE provides a global comparison of descriptor sequences, while PCC evaluates mutual trajectories, identifying how descriptors vary concurrently, whether in the same or opposite directions. Different methods are applied to process the Mel-scaled spectrum and the onsets for rhythm detection. For example, the comparison of the Mel-scaled spectrum utilizes the difference between the sequence of descriptors, or the percentage of overlap between two normal distribution derived from center of mass and variance of the two transforms over the whole segment. The onset descriptors are used to compute the binary rhythm of the sequence (Toussaint et al., 2004), quantizing the analyzed segments into a predefined number of intervals, typically $W = 16$, dividing each bar into sixteen equal segments, and associating each intervals with a 0 or 1 based on the presence of at least an onset in the interval. The resulting binary rhythms are compared utilizing MSE and Hamming distance methods.

The computation of each $c()$ is fine-tuned through specialized audio pre-processing and descriptor post-processing stages. Normalization occurs at various stages to ensure the metric’s range is between 0 and 1, rescaling descriptors and/or comparison results from their original ranges into the range $[0, 1]$ with min-max normalization toward uniform interpretation across metrics. Due to these intricacies, a universal mathematical formula for all metrics is not feasible, but individual metric details are documented in the publicly available source code. The model’s modularity, mirrored in its implementation, facilitates the addition of new comparison metrics. For metrics using PCC, correlation values (originally between -1 and 1 are normalized to fit within $[0, 1]$, where 0.5 indicates zero correlation, 1 indicates maximum positive correlation, and 0 , maximum negative correlation.

3.3 Macro-structural behavior

The MAAL makes decisions at the *meso*-level of perception, but the system’s decisions regarding the sequence of loops shape the *macro* structure of the performance, the *form* co-created by the musician and the MAAL. As discussed earlier, the MAAL provides settings that collectively influence its *macro*-structural behavior, summarized in Table 2. A representation of the the macro-structural behavior with three loop tracks ($N = 3$) is shown in Figure 2 as a Moore finite-state machine. Each of the 2^N states is depicted with a binary pattern, where 0_n indicates an empty audio buffer in loop track L_n , and 1_n signifies non-empty. State transitions occur every T_u when a new segment $s[m]$ is evaluated. Inputs determining the next state, and consequently the MAAL’s output, are:

- I_n : Segment placed on track L_n ’s audio buffer according to initialization update rule 8.
- A_n : Segment placed on track L_n ’s audio buffer according to update rule 7.
- Z_n : Track L_n ’s audio buffer cleared.
- R : Segment does not satisfy any update rule.

Figure 2: Finite-state machine illustrating the time behavior of the MAAL with three loop tracks. In the figure, the state of the MAAL is determined by the number of active loop tracks, showing how the system’s states can evolve over time. However, the musical possibilities of the system and the probability of transitions at any given moment are largely dependent on the rule sets associated to each track, the musician’s style and instrument they play, which determines the musical content of each loop track.

Figure 2 illustrates the wide range of possibilities with three loop tracks. The diagram suggests that the number of states and state transitions, and consequently the system’s complexity and unpredictability during a performance, grow significantly with the number of tracks. The system can occupy numerous states, each potentially resulting in distinct musical and aesthetic outcomes. This variation fosters exploration and offers dynamic paths for musical dialogue between the musician and the MAAL. However, this complexity might hinder meaningful understanding and influence over the system. Strategies for tuning the MAAL settings to achieve intended behavior are further discussed in Sections 5, 6, and 7, showcasing examples with larger numbers of loop tracks.

Table 2: Summary of the global system settings. The table includes two nested for loops, indicating the need to define comparison metrics, thresholds, and coefficients for all the rules utilized by the agent of each loop track.

Global parameter	Range of values
Length of analyzed segment in number of beats (T_u)	$T_u \in \mathbb{N}$
Length of loop audio buffer in number of beats (T_l)	$T_l \in \mathbb{N}$
Number of loop tracks (N)	$N \in \mathbb{N}$
Rhythmic subdivisions (W)	$W \in \mathbb{N} : W \in (4, 64)$
Number of self-comparisons for initialization rule (P)	$P \in \mathbb{N}$
Threshold for initialization rule (ϵ)	$\epsilon \in \mathbb{R} : \epsilon \in [0, 1]$
Minimum number of loop repetitions (r_{min})	$r_{min} \in \mathbb{N}$
Maximum number of loop repetitions (r_{max})	$r_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$
Number of rules for each loop track	$\{J_n \in \mathbb{N} : n \in [1, N], n \in \mathbb{N}\}$
for n in $[1, N]$	
for j in $[1, J_n]$	
Comparison metric ($ID_{j,n}$ from Table 1)	$ID \in \mathbb{N} : ID_{j,n} \in [1, 16]$
Comparison threshold ($\tau_{j,n}$)	$\tau_{j,n} \in \mathbb{R} : \tau_{j,n} \in [0, 1]$
Comparison coefficient ($\xi_{j,n}$)	$\xi_{j,n} \in \{-1, 1\}$

4 Implementation

4.1 Offline MAAL

The offline version of the MAAL simulates the live functioning of the system, using audio files as input and output. The model described in Section 3 is fully implemented in Python, utilizing the Librosa library (McFee et al., 2015) to compute descriptors. A configuration file is used to set the values for global settings listed in Table 2.

The system’s input is a mono audio file containing the musician’s signal. The output consists of a set of audio files, each corresponding to a loop track and having a duration identical to the input file. These output files are formed by rendering the contents of the loop track audio buffers throughout the input file’s duration. Additionally, the system generates waveform visualizations for the loop tracks, aiding in the identification of when and which segments were selected by the agents for looping. As previously discussed, the MAAL requires a metronome to synchronize and align all operations to be executed every interval, specifically at durations equal to the segment length (T_u). For the offline MAAL, we assume that the musician performed with a fixed tempo throughout the recorded performance and that the first audio sample of the file aligns with the first beat. Consequently, it is sufficient to provide the tempo in beats-per-minute (BPM) value to the offline MAAL as an additional parameter.

The offline implementation is primarily designed to facilitate the exploration, assessment, and tuning of the system’s behavior with regard to various global settings, particularly the rules employed by each track’s agent. While sound material can be generated using the offline MAAL, its main objective is to provide a systematic and reproducible means of adjusting global settings and rule sets to achieve specific musical objectives, which can later be applied in the live system. A key drawback of the offline version is that it uses a pre-recorded input signal, in which a musician cannot respond by adapting to the MAAL’s decisions and audio output—a dynamic interaction that is only possible in a live implementation.

4.2 Online MAAL

The online version of the MAAL is implemented using Pure Data (PD) along with the Python implementation. PD handles live sound recording to audio buffers, computation of descriptors, and playback from these buffers. Descriptors are computed using the Flucoma library for PD (Tremblay et al., 2022). The core functionalities of the MAAL are implemented in Python, where agents make decisions based on observed audio features. Communication between Python and PD occurs via the Open Sound Control protocol (OSC). The live version utilizes the same configuration file as the

offline counterpart, which is read by the Python script at startup and used to initialize global variables in both Python and PD.

The sound from a live musician is continuously recorded in a PD buffer. Each loop track is associated to a separate PD buffer, all of which are continuously playing. Each time one of these buffers, with a duration of T_u , is filled, the entire set of descriptors is computed in PD and sent to Python via OSC. Since the MAAL requires a metronome to synchronize and align all operations to be executed every T_u , the live system can interface with an external metronome signal, which may be machine-generated or derived from the musician's sound analysis. Additionally, the system offers the option to generate the metronome signal internally by manually setting the tempo in BPM, allowing the musician to choose whether to listen to the metronome.

The online version of the MAAL can be utilized as a live performance system. The PD implementation enables integration within larger computer music systems, as the contents of PD buffers can be accessed by any PD functions for real-time processing during performances. The system also supports easy integration of additional manual controls for interacting with agents, such as temporarily inhibiting one or more agents or manually clearing one or more loop track audio buffers.

Both versions of the MAAL are available as open-source software at <https://github.com/vincenzomadaghiale/MAAL>.

5 Use cases

In this section, we illustrate the behavior of the MAAL in three representative musical use cases, each utilizing various instruments and repertoires, and consequently different choices on the parameter settings. The purpose of these cases is to show how the MAAL can be utilized to obtain different musical objectives, in terms of how the musical structure evolves throughout a co-performance with the MAAL. The first two use cases utilize the offline version of the MAAL, while the third uses the online version, featuring the first author acting as a musician in a co-creative dialogue with the system. The settings for the use cases have been established with specific objectives in mind, and iteratively refined through the offline MAAL, which allowed to find effective combinations of metrics. Video documentation is available for the three use cases, showcasing visualizations of the co-performances, and interactions with the system in the third case. The video can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/records/15835530>. Although these examples demonstrate the technical flexibility of the MAAL, they do not suffice to establish the system's co-creative characteristics, which require human evaluation (Karimi et al., 2018; Jordanous, 2012).

5.1 Melody

The settings in this use case focus specifically on melodic structures, where loop track interactions are inspired by principles of counterpoint and voice leading. The input of the offline MAAL is a recording of the beginning of the viola part of the first movement of Joseph Haydn's String Quartet in D major, Op.76 No.5, which is primarily monophonic¹. To facilitate time grid alignment, a MIDI version of the score was rendered to audio using a the free VST plugin "BBC Symphony Orchestra" by Spitfire Audio², emulating a viola. The values of the system parameters for this use case are summarized in Table 3.

In this use case, the three loop tracks L_1 , L_2 and L_3 have been assigned the same combination of comparison metrics. The combination of metrics #6 and #14 selects melodic phrases that have contrary motion to the concurrent loops, while being in a different frequency range. The thresholds have been set to slightly different values to ensure a wider range of selected segments. Metrics #1 and #15 ensure that the harmonic and rhythmic content of the loops are coherent to each other, i.e. that the loops combination does not sound out of tune and loops have coincident rhythmic onsets.

By listening to the soundtrack corresponding to this scenario, we can observe that the segments chosen by the MAAL for looping seem sufficiently rhythmically and harmonically coherent throughout the track, and they tend to occupy different frequency ranges as expected. As visible in Figure 3, in the beginning of the track, the contents of the three tracks are replaced after few repetitions, creating

¹Score retrieved from <https://imslp.org/>

²<https://www.spitfireaudio.com/bbcso>

(a) Global parameters.

Parameter	Value
T_u	8
T_l	8
N	3
W	16
P	3
ϵ	0.001
r_{min}	4
r_{max}	20

(b) Rule set ρ_n for each loop track.

Loop track (n)	Comparison metric (ID)	Comparison threshold (τ)	Comparison coefficient (ξ)
1	#1	0.005	1
	#6	0.45	-1
	#14	0.9	-1
	#15	0.1	1
2	#1	0.008	1
	#6	0.35	-1
	#14	0.85	-1
	#15	0.1	1
3	#1	0.005	1
	#6	0.45	-1
	#14	0.95	-1
	#15	0.1	1

Table 3: Parameter settings for the melody use case, employing the metrics Harmonic similarity (#1), Melodic trajectory - D (#6), Frequency range overlap (#14), and Rhythmic similarity (#15) in a MAAL with $N = 3$ loop tracks.

Figure 3: Visualization of the chosen segments and contents of loop tracks in the melody example, using the offline MAAL.

a dynamic macro-structural evolution, which becomes more stable as the track progresses and the MAAL selects segments that interlock together better according to its comparison metrics; for this reason, the content of L_1 and L_3 is dropped only when r_{max} repetitions are exceeded.

5.2 Rhythm

This use case is an example of possible settings of the MAAL with a focus on rhythmic structures, where the musician is a jazz drummer. We tune the MAAL to listen to rhythmic properties of the sound material such as the regularity, density and dynamics of events in sound sequences. The recording employed to test this scenario is taken from the Groove dataset (Gillick et al., 2019). The values of the system parameters for this use case are summarized in Table 4.

In this use case, L_1 , L_2 and L_3 have the same metric combinations, with different thresholds. These three loop tracks form the main rhythmic structure, as they aim to select segments with distinct rhythms and timbres, identifying distinct drums or cymbals of the drum set, and varying rhythmic patterns. L_4 acts as an additional layer that reinforces the accents already present in the overall rhythmic structure, selecting segments with similar rhythm but different density and dynamics. This is evident by listening to the associated media file, observing the interplay between the audio tracks and their waveform visualization, displayed in Figure 4. Different loop tracks select segments that

(a) Global parameters.

Parameter	Value
T_u	4
T_l	4
N	4
W	32
P	3
ϵ	0.005
r_{min}	4
r_{max}	20

(b) Rule set ρ_n for each loop track.

Loop track (n)	Comparison metric (ID)	Comparison Threshold (τ)	Comparison coefficient (ξ)
1	#10	0.001	-1
	#15	0.8	-1
2	#10	0.002	-1
	#15	0.7	-1
3	#10	0.003	-1
	#15	0.6	-1
4	#7	0.05	-1
	#15	0.6	1
	#16	0.05	-1

Table 4: Parameter settings for the rhythm use case, employing the metrics Dynamic similarity (#7), Timbral similarity (#10) Rhythmic similarity (#15) and Rhythmic density (#16). We set the number of loop tracks as $N = 4$ and the rhythmic subdivision coefficient $W = 32$ to obtain detailed rhythmic descriptions.

correspond to various components of the drum set, progressively replacing them with segments that better complement each other’s rhythmic structure.

Figure 4: Visualization of the chosen segments and contents of loop tracks in the rhythm example, using the offline MAAL.

5.3 Mixed

This use case provides an example of use of the online MAAL. The loop tracks in this example aim to mimic the functions of different instruments in a musical ensemble, employing a combination of rhythmic and timbral metrics. In this scenario, an amplified nylon-string acoustic guitar is utilized, played live by the first author of this paper alongside the online MAAL. The process of selecting and tuning the settings was first carried out using the offline MAAL, facilitated by a recording of the same instrument played by the same performer, and then fine-tuned through practice in the online setting. The values of the system parameters for this use case are summarized in Table 5.

L_1 and L_2 use metrics #10 and #15 with the objective of selecting segments with distinct timbres and rhythms with respect to the other loops. In this way, the selected segments are those played

(a) Global parameters.

Parameter	Value
T_u	4
T_l	4
N	6
W	16
P	3
ϵ	0.003
r_{min}	24
r_{max}	60

(b) Rule set ρ_n for each loop track.

Loop track (n)	Comparison metric (ID)	Comparison Threshold (τ)	Comparison coefficient (ξ)
1	#10	0.75	-1
	#15	0.75	-1
2	#10	0.76	-1
	#15	0.75	-1
3	#1	0.05	1
	#15	0.35	1
4	#1	0.05	1
	#15	0.3	1
5	#1	0.05	1
	#14	0.75	-1
	#15	0.35	1
6	#1	0.04	1
	#14	0.75	-1
	#15	0.5	1

Table 5: Parameter settings for the mixed-use case, using metrics Harmonic similarity (#1), Timbral similarity (#10), Frequency range overlap (#14) and Rhythmic similarity (#15). We employ $N = 6$ tracks in the system, and set $r_{min} = 24$ and $r_{max} = 60$, higher values with respect to the previous two examples, experimentally selected based on the author’s aesthetic preferences for the online scenario.

with different techniques, for example identifying and selecting strummed chords, arpeggios or melodic lines. L_3 and L_4 act as reinforcement of the rhythmic accents in the other tracks, selecting similar rhythms and harmonic content. L_5 and L_6 are similar to L_3 and L_4 , however they are further constrained on selecting segments in distinct frequency ranges, providing additional variation.

Because of the relatively large number of loop tracks used in this case ($N = 6$), we can clearly observe the global emergent characteristics of the system’s behavior from the recording of the demonstrative co-performance’s macro-structure. This can be noticed by observing how loop tracks respond to respective changes to the content of the other tracks. The macro-structure formed by the loops evolves irregularly from relatively long moments of stability reached when the loop tracks complement each other in a highly satisfactory structure according to the rule sets, to sections with faster dynamic changes when more drastic transitions occur. In the recorded demonstrative co-performance, the system reaches an equilibrium condition after an initial phase of instability, where new candidate segments are not accepted by any loop track until the loop in L_3 is dropped, prompting the other tracks to adapt towards a new equilibrium by selecting different segments. A similar equilibrium is reached again before the ending, when changes in one of the tracks do not affect the global equilibrium of the other tracks.

6 Discussion

The three use cases provided in this paper demonstrate the flexibility of the MAAL and allow us to obtain a preliminary view of its affordances, strengths, and weaknesses. From our initial experience, the large number of settings makes the MAAL a flexible system able to adapt to different instruments and styles. However, for the same reason, finding settings to achieve specific musical behaviors can be challenging. In general, not all comparison metrics can work well with all instruments, and finding the value ranges within which threshold values are musically meaningful can be time consuming, especially when testing rules composed of several metrics.

The global behavior of the MAAL is highly affected by the first segment selected in the initial state when the audio buffers of all loop tracks are empty. Indeed, the decisions of the agent controlling each loop track is dependent on the sonic nature of the concurrently looping segments, therefore the choice of the first loop has a strong impact on the behavior of the other loop tracks. This sensitivity to initial conditions is an aesthetic characteristic of the system’s expected behavior in response to specific sound materials, whose boundaries are defined by the predefined rules sets. This is a known property of multi-agent systems (Serugendo et al., 2005), and its musical implications have been previously investigated as chaotic systems (Slater, 1998; Hordijk, 2009). In our preliminary experiments with live interaction, this aspect can be interpreted positively, since it creates the possibility of widely different improvised performances using the same system settings, while keeping musical coherence. A clear limitation of the current system is that it is not able to adapt its decisions to changes in the human musician’s performance.

Overall, the system’s behavior is greatly influenced by the musician’s contextual decisions, necessitating an in-depth evaluation with musicians to accurately characterize its affordances as a co-creative system and its behavior in diverse musical contexts. The use cases presented in this paper are insufficient for assessing the user experience, and the experience of a user who is not a designer may significantly differ from that reported by the authors.

7 Conclusions

We designed the Multi-Agent Autonomous Looper to explore the creative possibilities arising from automating the function of loop selection in an improvised live looping performance. In this paper, we have presented a computational model representing the operation of a live looper, and we have proposed an automation method employing a rule-based multi-agent system based on machine listening.

In the future, we plan to evaluate the behavioral and co-creative aspects of the MAAL through structured user studies involving a diverse range of musicians. Currently, the most challenging aspect of the system is the selection and tuning process of rules and thresholds. We aim to address this by automating these processes using corpus-analysis methods, possibly extracting rules from user-provided looping examples or annotated performance recordings, allowing to tailor settings to individual use cases. To accomplish this, we will investigate the suitability of various AI approaches. Possible techniques include unsupervised learning, evolutionary algorithms, and reinforcement learning. Furthermore, we intend to explore dynamic rule adaptation for the agents and evaluate the impact of such adaptations throughout a performance, especially during stages where they adjust to the ongoing co-performance. Finally, we plan to enhance the system by expanding the range of comparison metrics and integrating a tempo-adaptive algorithm.

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